

Impact of Equities' Price Behaviour on Selected Commodity W.R.T. Zinc (Commodity) vs Hindustan Zinc (Equity) – An Indian Market Perspective

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Abstract : Indian Stock markets are growing rapidly as like stock exchanges in China, U.S. & UK etc. In earlier days the investment in stock market was less under coverage due to lack of knowledge in equity & other related options which related to stock markets. Even in stock exchanges there is a plethora of choices like investment in equity markets, commodities, debentures, mutual funds, exchange traded funds etc. Depending on the investors risk taking ability they are investing in different options. People like more risk, they may prefer investing in derivatives, commodities & exchange traded funds which has a very high risk & return too; whereas investors prefer less risk may go for mutual funds, debentures & equity market sometimes. This study will help the investors to compare commodity Zinc which is traded in commodities market like MCX, NCDEX, ICEX etc. with common equity stocks like Hindustan Zinc which are traded in equity markets like NSE & BSE. The main objective of the study is “To find the impact of the price behaviours of equities with the selected commodity”. The scope of the study is from this research, the investors can get a better conclusion on where to invest, which company can be invested, which sector is going good, what is the exact relationship between equity & commodity markets of same industry. The limitation is the times frame (6 Months) & cover only Indian perspective not on broader aspect. All the data are considered here are of parametric variables & samples in nature. The tools used are F-Test, Correlation & ANOVA etc. The finding says that there is a key relationship between the selected equity shares with corresponding commodity options. So it's better concluded that, the investors are advised to be rational than herding which means to use common sense & no group sense.

Keywords: Commodity Markets, Equity Markets, F-Test, Parametric Variables, Correlation, Strong relationship between commodity & equity markets etc.

JEL Classification Number: G10, G12, Q02

Introduction:

In the recent years the investments in stock markets are increased considerably. Notably developing countries like India has received a lump sum capital inflow in Equities Market. The LPG policy introduced on 1991 by Indian government made a boost in Indian Economy & stock markets as well. The Economy is decided by the corporate of different sectors. One who analyse stock markets carefully then this capital market will be the best investment opportunity though there are a lot of risk factors involved compared to other

investment opportunities. But this is where all the investors are making mistakes in analysing the equity market.

The Behavioral Finance of investors is playing a major role towards investment in stock markets in particular. The variations in capital markets are because of economic & non-economic issues in a country. This research is aimed for behavioral aspect of stock market investment patterns. This research project analyses the selected banking sectors in India which are listed in NSE India. It made an attempt to analyse the trend of the selected banking stocks. Needless to say there are so many banks listed in Nifty is the main indicator of trading in India. Many companies are raising money through IPO & that's why this research meant for.

About The Study

The study focuses on finding the impact of the price behaviour of equities with the selected commodities and comparative study between the commodities and equities with the reference to highly traded commodities and major companies highly invested by the public. The price behaviour of the company's equities are related with the products or commodities of the companies in the comparison. The analysis is made by comparing and contrasting the equity price behaviour of selected companies and the selected commodity that results with the major impact.

There is a high correlation between the price behaviour of the company's shares with the commodities of those companies. The market of the commodities is not impacted by only one company's equity price behaviour but also the major companies that has market as a whole industry or any specific sectors.

The price behaviour of London exchange market and United States market also had the major impact on the Indian commodities market. The study focuses on few sectors such as the crude oil, Base metals and the industrial goods where the equity price behaviour shows its reflection in their stocks.

Objectives of The Study

- To find the impact of the price behaviours of equities with the selected commodity
- To analyse the highly traded commodities with impact of equities of major companies
- To interpret the correlation of the price changes of equities with the commodities
- To provide the valuable information to investors to secure their investments
- To suggest the investors to avoid the risk and increase their returns

Industry Profile

Securities market is an organised market in terms of transaction of capital & commodity. Securities market can be divided into primary & secondary markets both are playing a very crucial role towards the development of Indian economy & its unavoidable.

Statement of Problem

There is a major impact of price behaviours of equities with the commodity market, where the problem stating that currency market slightly disturbs the impact, the increase in the currency value increases the price of the commodity.

The currency fluctuations disturb the price behaviours of the commodity and also may reduce the correlation between both the equity market and the commodity market.

Scope of The Study

- The study scopes the commodity traders to realise the impact of equities price behaviours.
- The study scopes to the investors to understand the major impact created in the commodity market reflects their company.
- The equities price behaviours alerts the commodity traders to anticipate the market in prior and trade according to the changes.
- The currency disturbances on impact of equity and commodity price behaviours.
- The study is very simple and is easy to understand for further research on the comparative analysis of the equity price behaviour with the commodity.

Review Of Literature

Marco J Lombardi (2022): Studied about the correlation between the commodities, equities and derivatives -Density forecasts, the author utilised density forecast for the data and came out with the result of correlation between the three variables where there is a major impact with each other.

S.Sathya (2021): Comparative study on equity, commodity and currency derivatives and also compared risk and returns among stocks, using fundamental and technical analysis with the variant correlation, cointegration and resulted with the major impact on the stocks and risk of the stocks.

Micheal S. Haigh (March 2022): “Market as one” studied relation between the returns on the investable commodity and U.S. equity that have been changed in preceding years using the dynamic correlation and the recursive cointegration techniques and came out with the positive result.

Kilian (2023): In the segment of commodities, however, financial investors may have less commodity specific knowledge and a different attitude compared to commercial players, and hence enter or exit trades based on their overall perceptions of the macroeconomic situation rather than market specific factors. If this is the case, it would suggest that commodity prices are increasingly influenced by shocks coming from the demand side. This is a well-established fact in the literature on oil, following the seminal work by Kilia. The fact that equity prices are also likely to have been largely driven by shocks related to the global economic activity, especially in the aftermath of the financial crisis, could then explain the increase in correlations.

Research Methodology

Type Of Research

Analytical research is adopted for analyzing the past data of the share price of the companies from BSE, NSE, MCXCOM and NCDEX markets with various technical indicators to predict the short term price movements of the scripts. Analytical research is a detailed type of research that involves critical thinking skills and the assessment of facts and information comparative to the research being conducted.

Data And Sources Of Data

Since its finance based research & dealing in numbers, secondary data from the NSE, BSE, MCXCOM, & NCDEX markets is used for the research. The historical data prices are sourced from www.nseindia.com, moneycontrol.com, investing.com and the Coimbatore Capitals Websites.

Time Period Covered

The research is carried for the period of three months from February 2016 to the April 2019, which covers three years. The historical Data of the commodities collected are the weekly data of every week Tuesday and are compared with the equity price behaviours. The scripts are also collected according to the expiry of particular commodities in the Indian market.

Population

All the scripts in the NSE, BSE, MCXCOMM and the NCDEX are collected for the study for the population and the method of census are used for the study. The population size in the study is the selected major companies with different sectors and is compared with the selected related commodities respectively to the sectors. They are

- Hindusthan Zinc
- ONGC
- Sakthi Sugars
- Vedanta Ltd
- Gravita Ltd &
- Hindcopper

And the commodities compared with the above companies are

- Zinc
- Light Sweet crude oil
- Sugar

Hypothesis Formation

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant differences exists between Equity and Commodity shares (this hypothesis are common for both correlation and F- test tools).

Alternative Hypothesis (H_a): There is a significant differences exists between Equity and commodity shares.

Statistical Tools Used

The research focuses on few of the technical indicators for the research of the equity price behaviours and the commodities prices with the chart patterns. The tools are:

- The Bivariate Correlations (γ) methods &
- The Fisher Test of the Correlation (F – Test) methods
- ANOVA

Bivariate Correlation

Bivariate correlation is a measure of the relationship between the two variables it measures the strength of their relationship, which can range from absolute value 1 to 0.

$$r = r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

F-Test (The Fisher Test)

An F-test is any statistical test in which the test statistic has an F-distribution under the null hypothesis.

a) Hypothesis Formation:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): Both Equity & Commodity shares’ have the same variances.

b) Formulas:

$$F = S_1^2 / S_2^2$$

Where, $S_1^2 = \Sigma (X_1 - \bar{X}_1)^2 / (n_1 - 1)$ Here, $n_1 = n_2 = 10$

$S_2^2 = \Sigma (X_2 - \bar{X}_2)^2 / (n_2 - 1)$ L.O.S. (α) = 1%

$\bar{X}_1 = \Sigma X_1 / n_1$ & $\bar{X}_2 = \Sigma X_2 / n_2$

c) Testing the Hypothesis:

If the Calculated Value < Table Value, Then Accept “H₀”

Limitations Of The Study

- This study uses only Bivariate Correlation and Fisher test for correlation and is limited with analysis of correlation.
- This study is limited with the three sectors Crude oil, Base metals, Sugar and the price behaviours of those sectors.
- This study is limited to selected commodities and the scripts are related to the selected company’s equity share prices.

4. Analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Bivariate Correlation

Table 4.1.1: Zinc & Hind Zinc

Date (Weekly)	HINDZINC (Equity)	ZINC (Commodity)
Mar-22	324	276
Jun-22	275	290
Sep-22	290	310
Dec-22	310	320
Mar-23	325	330
Jun-23	340	340
Sep-23	355	350
Dec-23	370	360
Mar-24	385	370
Jun-24	400	380
Sep-24	415	390
Dec-24	430	400
Total	$\Sigma X=1208.35$	$\Sigma Y=1567.94$

$$r = r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Where $\Sigma x = 1208.35$

$\Sigma y = 1567.94$

Correlation (γ) = **0.040476**

The Bivariate Correlation found for above historical data for the commodity of zinc and the equity price behaviour of Hindustan Zinc is **0.040476**. As the value range between the 0 and 1 and the range is positive, the correlation is ‘**Positive Correlation**’.

Chart: Zinc & Hindzinc

Interpretation:

The above chart represents the correlation between the equity price behaviour and the commodity, Zinc and the Hind Zinc respectively. There is a positive correlation between the variables, 'X' Axis represents the price behaviour of Hind zinc and Y Axis represents the price of Zinc where there is correlation in the price behaviour. Hence there is a major impact of equity price in commodity price. As the value range between the 0 and 1 and the range is positive, the correlation is 'Positive Correlation'.

F - Test (The Fisher Test)

Zinc & Hind Zinc

a) Hypothesis Formation:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): Both Equity (Hind Zinc) & Commodity (Zinc) shares' have the same variances.

b) Formulas:

$$F = S_1^2 / S_2^2$$

Where, $S_1^2 = \Sigma (\overline{X}_1 - \overline{X}_1)^2 / (n_1 - 1)$

$$S_2^2 = \Sigma (\overline{X}_2 - \overline{X}_2)^2 / (n_2 - 1)$$

$$X_1 = \Sigma X_1 / n_1 \quad \& \quad X_2 = \Sigma X_2 / n_2$$

Here, $n_1 = n_2 = 10$

L.O.S. (α) = 1%

c) Testing the Hypothesis:

If the Calculated Value < Table Value, Then Accept “H₀”

d) Tabulation to Find S₁² & S₂² (To Find the Calculated Value (CV)):

Table 4.2.1: Fishers Test

Date (Weekly)	Hind Zinc (X ₁)	Zinc (X ₂)	(X ₁ - \bar{X}_1)	(X ₁ - \bar{X}_1) ²	(X ₂ - \bar{X}_2) ²	(X ₂ - \bar{X}_2) ²
23/10/2024	523.70	124.75	9.156	83.83	3.91	15.29
14/10/2024	520.20	117.2	3.306	10.93	-3.64	13.25
07/10/2024	495.40	123.35	4.256	18.11	2.51	6.30
30/09/2024	522.50	119.65	-9.034	81.61	-1.19	1.42
25/09/2024	511.20	122.45	-7.334	53.79	1.61	2.59
18/09/2024	485.00	120.95	-9.384	88.06	0.11	0.01
10/09/2024	486.85	123.2	-5.634	31.74	2.36	5.57
03/09/2024	500.75	120.9	6.056	36.68	0.06	0.00
27/08/2024	492.55	120	7.406	54.85	-0.84	0.71
20/08/2024	485.90	115.9	1.206	1.45	-4.94	24.40
Total	1567.94	1208.35	0	461.06	0	69.54

e) Calculations:

$$\bar{X}_1 = 1567.94 / 10 = 156.794 \quad \& \quad \bar{X}_2 = 1208.35 / 10 = 120.835$$

$$S_1^2 = 461.06 / 9 = 51.23 \quad \& \quad S_2^2 = 69.54 / 9 = 7.73$$

$$F = 51.23 / 7.73 = 6.6300$$

Hence, **F_{CV} = 6.6300**

f) To Find the Table Value (TV):

$$m = n_1 - 1 = 10 - 1 = 9 \quad \& \quad n = n_2 - 1 = 10 - 1 = 9$$

@ 1% L.O.S. (α), **F_{TV} = 5.3511**

g) Interpretation:

$$F_{CV} = 6.6300 \quad \& \quad F_{TV} = 5.3511$$

Here, F_{CV} > F_{TV}

Since the Calculated Value is greater than the Table Value **we have to reject the “H₀”.**

h) Conclusion:

Both Equity (Hind Zinc) & Commodity (Zinc) shares’ have the different variances.

a) Hypothesis Formation:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): Both Equity (ONGC) & Commodity (Crude Oil) shares' have the same variances.

b) Formulas:

$$F = S_1^2 / S_2^2$$

Where, $S_1^2 = \Sigma (X_1 - \bar{X}_1)^2 / (n_1 - 1)$

$$S_2^2 = \Sigma (X_2 - \bar{X}_2)^2 / (n_2 - 1)$$

$$\bar{X}_1 = \Sigma X_1 / n_1 \quad \& \quad \bar{X}_2 = \Sigma X_2 / n_2$$

Here, $n_1 = n_2 = 10$

L.O.S. $\alpha = 1\%$

c) Testing the Hypothesis:

If the Calculated Value < Table Value, Then Accept "H₀"

d) Calculations:

$$\bar{X}_1 = 2083.75 / 10 = 208.375 \quad \& \quad \bar{X}_2 = 363.47 / 10 = 36.347$$

$$S_1^2 = 472.39 / 9 = 52.49 \quad \& \quad S_2^2 = 170.58 / 9 = 18.95$$

$$F = 52.49 / 18.95 = 2.7693$$

Hence, **F_{CV} = 2.7693**

e) To Find the Table Value (TV):

$$m = n_1 - 1 = 10 - 1 = 9 \quad \& \quad n = n_2 - 1 = 10 - 1 = 9$$

@ 1% L.O.S. (α), **F_{TV} = 5.3511**

f) Interpretation:

$$F_{CV} = 2.7693 \quad \& \quad F_{TV} = 5.3511$$

Here, F_{CV} < F_{TV}

Since the Calculated Value is less than the Table Value **we have to accept the "H₀".**

g) Conclusion:

Both Equity (ONGC) & Commodity (Crude Oil) shares' have the same variances.

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

Findings

Zinc & hind zinc

- The Historical data of the ten weeks are collected and compared with the equity price behaviour and the commodity where there is a major impact.

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- Hindzinc company's share price fluctuations highly affect the commodity market of zinc.
- There is a positive correlation of **0.040476**, which ranges between 1 and the 0. There is a greatest impact of price behaviour of equity in the commodity.

Suggestions

- The commodity traders are suggested to observe the equity market before they buy or sell in long or short scripts.
- There is a high impact of the equity price behaviour with the commodity and there is a need to track the equity prices of the companies in Indian Stock Market. Investors are asked to so cautious.
- There is an impact of both fundamental and technical movements in the Indian stock market & so the investors to be careful.

Conclusion

The study on impact of the equity price behaviour with the commodity are concluded successfully stating that there is a major impact on each other and the investors and the traders can analyse the trend and trade according to the movements of the market. There is low risk when the traders refer to the equity price behaviour of the particular sectors to protect and prevent their investment from loses and successfully attain the highest returns in the commodity market. The changes in currency disturb the impact and hence observation on currency is also important for the traders.

This research is in the preliminary level. There is always a broader scope of extending this research by increasing number of weeks, raw data, collecting more review of literature, & adding more tools. In a limited period of time, this research made a valiant attempt to identify the relationship between the commodities with selected equities & also offered some useful suggestions to the investors those who are reading this research. Finally, only by correlation phenomenon this research found a relationship between commodity & equity & so this result can be debated by adding more statistical tools for analysis & give better results.

References:

1. Ampereyannasreeram, A., Anusha, L., and Leela, M. 2024, Impact of equities on commodities: A study using Johansen cointegration test. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 12(1), 45–58.
2. Cassassus, J., and Higuera, D. 2011, Oil prices and stock returns. *Energy Economics*, 33(3), 363–370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2010.11.005>
3. Chang, C.-L., McAleer, M., and Tansuchat, R. 2011, Crude oil hedging strategies using dynamic multivariate GARCH. *Energy Economics*, 33(5), 912–923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2011.01.009>
4. Della Corte, P., Sarno, L., and Tsiakas, I. 2012, Oil price density forecasts: Exploring the linkages with stock markets. *Journal of Econometrics*, 158(1), 103–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2010.12.001>
5. Gorton, G., and Rouwenhorst, K. G. 2006, Facts and fantasies about commodity futures. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 62(2), 47–68. <https://doi.org/10.2469/faj.v62.n2.4083>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15206240>

6. Haigh, M. S., & Holt, M. T. (2007). Do agricultural commodity futures prices influence equity returns? *Journal of Futures Markets*, 27(9), 863–883.
7. Haigh, M. S., and Hranaiova, J. 2007, Market integration and contagion: A study of the U.S. and U.K. equity markets. *Commodity Futures Trading Commission*.
8. http://file.scirp.org/pdf/ME20110300014_43128952.pdf
9. <http://in.investing.com/commodities/copper>
10. <http://www.bis.org/publ/work420.pdf>
11. https://www1.nseindia.com/live_market/dynaContent/live_watch/get_quotehttp://www.coimbatorecapital.com/Markets/Gainers-and-Losers/GAIN/BSE
12. Kilian, L. 2009, Not all oil price shocks are alike: Disentangling demand and supply shocks in the crude oil market. *American Economic Review*, 99(3), 1053–1069. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.99.3.1053>
13. Kilian, L., and Park, C. 2009, The impact of oil price shocks on the U.S. stock market. *International Economic Review*, 50(4), 1267–1287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2354.2009.00568.x>
14. Lombardi, M. J., & Ravazzolo, F. (2016). On the correlation between commodity and equity returns: Implications for portfolio allocation. *Journal of Commodity Markets*, 1(1), 45–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomm.2015.12.001>
15. Lombardi, M. J., and Ravazzolo, F. 2013, On the correlation between commodity and equity returns: Implications for portfolio allocation. *BIS Working Paper No. 420*. Bank for International Settlements. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2384446>
16. Sathya, S. 2015, A comparative study on equity, commodity, currency derivatives in India—Evidence from future market with special reference to BSE Ltd, Mumbai. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 3(2), 2175–2182. <https://ijsrm.net/index.php/ijsrm/article/view/149>